

Title: Challenges and Thoughts in Making Text Ground Truth for Republican Chinese Newspaper -- Taking *Jing Bao* as an example

中文标题：民国报纸文本基准真值制作的挑战与思考——以《晶报》为例

Author:

XIE Jia 谢佳

University of Heidelberg

ORCID: 0000-0002-3609-5019

jia.xie@stud.uni-heidelberg.de

YIP Suk Man 葉淑敏

University of Heidelberg

ysmlouis@msn.com

Funding:

This research has received partial funding from the Research Council of Field of Focus 3 “Cultural Dynamics in Globalised Worlds” (FoF 3) of the University of Heidelberg.

Development of the Early Chinese Periodicals Online (ECPO) project was partially supported by the Excellence Initiative of the German Research Foundation (DFG), Cluster of Excellence “Asia and Europe in a Global Context”, and the Heidelberg Centre for Transcultural Studies, Heidelberg University.

Abstract

Many researchers explored the use of machine learning for optical character recognition (OCR), particularly in Europe and North America, and many projects are producing ground truth (GT) data for this purpose. It is different when it comes to non-Latin script (NLS) material.^[1] The Early Chinese Periodicals Online (ECPO) project at the University of Heidelberg started to work on ways to produce machine-readable full text from historical Chinese newspapers in 2021. ECPO uses different machine-learning approaches, including convolutional neural networks, to develop a semi-automatic pipeline to produce machine-

readable full text. We chose the entertainment newspaper *Jing Bao* (*The Crystal*, 1919-1940) as the basis for our experiments.

Our paper focuses on two main aspects: Firstly, we provide a description of our ground truth editing work. It includes assembling the editing team, organizing the workflows, establishing processing regulations, and ensuring quality control. Secondly, we discuss particular challenges in producing the GT sets, including issues in character encoding and problems with variant characters related to Unicode. We produced two sets of ground truth data comprising textual/structural data (full-text GT) and segmentation data (geometry GT). We hope our experiences from the project can be helpful to others working with NLS material. Based on our work, we point out some pitfalls and provide hints to avoid them in order to make machine learning more efficient.

Keywords: Ground Truth, Republican Chinese Newspapers, Jing Bao, OCR

1 Introduction

This paper is about a project of editing the ground truth, which is for the machine-learning task of developing the ground truth for establishing an automatic OCR system for Republican Chinese newspapers. Ground truth (GT) is a term used in the field of machine learning and can be understood as a set of correctly-labeled data that guide supervised machine learning to approach the expected result. Therefore, good GT must be free of flaws. The essential issue of this project is the written language of Chinese because the scripts are significantly different from the Latin alphabet, which Magner has stated through comparison.^[2] In recent years, more scholars have paid attention to the bias in the academic Digital Humanities (DH) field towards the English language,^[3] language indifference and multilingual DH.^{[4][1]} The experience with English and Latin scripts is inapplicable to Chinese material, which is why we conducted our project.

The project “Building Ground Truth for the Early Chinese Periodicals Online (ECPO)” was

funded by the Research Council *Cultural Dynamics in Globalized Worlds*¹ at the University of Heidelberg. Some of its background information and details can be found in Matthias Arnold's presentation at the Association for Asian Studies 2021 Virtual Annual Conference (AAS 2021).^[5] The larger ECPO² project is one of the outstanding DH achievements of the Centre for Asian and Transcultural Studies (CATS), which provides Republican periodicals as well as data of the agents in an open-access web platform.^[6] In recent years, ECPO started investigating approaches to producing full-text data from early Chinese newspapers using machine learning and neural networks. To apply computational methods to page segmentation, character detection, and character recognition, a set of high-quality GT is necessary.

At present, a number of institutions in China have successively carried out projects on digitization and full-text OCR of Republican newspapers. The more well-known ones include the National Library. Zhang Wei, in discussing the acceptance of the digitization of Republican newspapers, introduces the situation about metadata and layout division, and analyzes the reasons for the poor digitization correctness.^[7] Cao Xinxin's article describes the process and common problems of the National Library of China in OCR work on Republican newspapers and puts forward suggestions for improvement.^[8] In addition, the work of Shanghai Library's Republic of China database is also excellent, and Xiao Hong et al. clearly show their steps and some typical errors in dealing with Republic of China newspapers and periodicals, which also give rich examples of common problems of OCR.^[9] All these valuable experiences provide great insights to our work.

This paper has three purposes. First, we describe the process of organizing our editing team. The task was to record samples of a Republican Chinese tabloid with encoded files for machine learning. Our team, including two supervisors and two editors, was responsible for inputting, editing, and proofreading the data from samples issued in April 1920 and April 1930, ensuring the characters and layouts input in the files were the same as those printed on the tabloids.

Secondly, this paper states the problems we encountered and their solutions. We found

¹ The details of this research focus can be seen at <https://www.uni-heidelberg.de/en/research/research-profile/fields-of-focus/field-of-focus-iii/research-council>

² Early Chinese Periodicals Online, <https://uni-heidelberg.de/ecpo>

various issues during the inputting, editing, and proofreading processes, such as the variants (異體字, or *Yitizi*)³, the recognition of illegible or rare characters, varied reading directions, etc. Collaborating with the technical supporting team, the editing team gradually built up a set of regulations⁴ to cope with the situations that mostly happened in Chinese material.

Last but not least, we share our whole workflow experience with those doing similar tasks. This paper elaborates on recruiting, training, and supervising editors with access to our tutorials and documents. We hope our work can be a good template or inspire people interested in DH of non-Latin scripts to consider how to fulfill their projects.

1.1 Choosing *Jing Bao* for the Ground Truth

The project selects a Republican Chinese tabloid (小報, or *Xiaobao*), *Jing Bao* 晶報, as the raw materials to produce the GT for machine learning of reading traditional Chinese. *Jing Bao*, which was established in Shanghai in March 1919, was praised as the “King of Tabloid” (小報之王, or *Xiaobao zhi wang*) in the 1930s because of its bold style^[10]. Yu Daxiong 余大雄, the chief editor, insisted on the principle that *Jing Bao* would publish all the articles that other newspapers dared not or did not want to print. Although it was eventually closed in May 1940 due to the drop in sales, it was still one of the most influential tabloids in the Republican period. Apart from its reputation and influence, its non-stop publication for more than twenty years is the main reason for choosing it for the ground truth of the OCR system.⁵ Therefore, the team decided to input two months of the tabloid issued in April 1920 and April 1930. Adding the ten issues in April 1939, which had been processed earlier,⁶ we can easily compare the changes in the page layout, typographic design and character use in this Republican tabloid within thirty years. Due to its abundant content, both in texts and images, we believe it could be an ideal material for our project. The version of *Jing Bao* we used is in

³ Yitizi is the variants that are not the standard characters (*Zhengzi*, 正字), see 教育部異體字字典. https://dict.variants.moe.edu.tw/variants/rbt/page_content3.do?pageId=2982201

⁴ the details of the regulations are on the WIKI page of ECPO GitHub repository, see <https://github.com/hcts-hra/ecpo-data/wiki>

⁵ It was suspended for three months in 1937 because of the censorship of the Japanese Army.

⁶ The editing work of *Jing Bao* 1939 April was prior to our task but did not finish until we were involved in it.

the ECPO database, and meanwhile, we also checked another version from other sources.

Jing Bao was issued every three days from the 1920s to the early 1930s, so there are ten issues monthly. Each issue has four pages: pages 1 and 4 are advertisements, and pages 2 and 3 are articles from contributors. We chose the article pages as samples, which include a total of 40 pages. In November 1933, *Jing Bao* was reformed and changed to issue daily.

Therefore, the ten issues in April 1939 were published in consecutive ten days from April 21 to 30. Each issue has eight pages, and the advertisements were scattered on every page, mainly on the second half page and the middle parts between two pages. Since articles appear on every page, all eight pages of the issues in April 1939, 80 pages total, are included in the machine-learning task.

Thus, there are a total of 120 pages of traditional Chinese articles from the Republican tabloid issued in April 1920, 1930 and 1939. With these 120 pages of Chinese characters and typographic format as a primary source, we hope that it can establish a more sensitive and accurate OCR system for traditional Chinese newspapers.

1.2 Team and Schedule

The editing team includes the project leader Matthias Arnold, two Ph.D students, YIP Suk Man and XIE Jia, also the two authors of this paper, as supervisors, and two undergraduate editors. Here is the detail of the project plan. Initially, the two supervisors are taught about file formats, software usage, etc. Then they recruit suitable student assistants from the university as editors to join the team. The two supervisors should have expert knowledge of traditional Chinese characters. The student assistants are expected to have native Chinese proficiency to recognize and type complex characters as well as fluent English for communication. After confirming the team members, we label the two editors as groups A and B for independent entry work, which is the blind double-keying mode. Every Monday the two supervisors and the two editors have a meeting to share difficulties and doubts that arose from the weekly work. In the beginning, the weekly workload is to enter 2 pages of articles from one issue of the newspaper.

Dates	Events	Total of Time
-------	--------	---------------

2021/10/01-2021/10/10	Recruited new editors: posted recruit ads; launched a job interview	10 days
2021/10/16-2021/11/06*	Conducted a training course for two new editors: 4 lessons on four consecutive Saturdays;	4 weeks
2021/10/16-2022/01/31*	data entry and editing of <i>Jing Bao</i> (1930 April): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2021/10/16-2021/12/28: two editors, data entry P2&3; two supervisors, data entry P1&4 • 2022/01/01-2022/01/31: two supervisors, editing and proofreading P1&4; P2&3 	3.5 months (2.5 months + 1 month)
2022/01/01-2022/03/15*	data entry and editing of <i>Jing Bao</i> (1920 April): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2022/01/01-2022/02/28: two editors, data entry P2&3; two supervisors, data entry P1&4 • 2022/03/01-2022/03/15: two supervisors, editing and proofreading P1&4; P2&3 	2.5 months (2 months + 0.5 month)

Table 1. Project Schedule

As the table demonstrates, the project lasted 5 months, from October 16, 2021, to March 15, 2022.⁷ Within the five months, other than recruiting and training new editors, we (supervisors) also finished editing and proofreading the GT files they produced. Due to the gradual familiarity with the content of the work, the editors can improve their efficiency with time, and the task was completed smoothly as expected.

1.3 Software and Platform

Our data is saved in XML (extensional markup language) format. GitHub is the central platform we use to store and operate the data. The data produced in this project are all open-access and can be found in the “ECPO” repository of the organization HCTS.⁸ In the “issues” section, we post questions and ideas that arose in the course of our work and discuss them with technical members. In addition, we set up several “wiki” pages for this repository. These

⁷ The training course and the data entry of *Jing Bao* 1930 April were done simultaneously. When the editing and proofreading of *Jing Bao* 1930 April was processed in January 2022, the data entry of *Jing Bao* 1920 April started.

⁸ <https://github.com/exc-asia-and-europe/ecpo>

pages function as a comprehensive tutorial, containing the standards and explanations of our work in general, such as workflow, codes for reference, and many other valuable notes.

We choose Oxygen XML Editor as our editing software. The original image files are then shared by HeiBox, a cloud drive service provided by the University of Heidelberg. Through online data exchange, we can work very flexibly and efficiently. Even under strict epidemic policies, everything could run smoothly.⁹

2 Implementation of the Project

In this GT editing project, two supervisors were responsible for guiding two editors to type the proper codes and characters. To enhance the sensitivity and accuracy of the OCR system, the supervisors need to ensure the inputs are correct and the files are in legal structure.

2.1 Recruiting

To fulfill the project, we recruited two undergraduate students as editors under our project funding. Their job was for the data entry of *Jing Bao* issued in April 1920 and April 1930. The two editors were labeled as two independent groups for blind double-keying, which was designed to allow for later file comparison to find differences and identify more complex issues. Our target was to hire two Chinese-native undergraduate students who could read traditional Chinese. There were not many specific criteria, but we agreed that those who had experience in inputting Chinese documents and are familiar with traditional Chinese should be the better choices.

We started to spread our recruitment news at the beginning of October 2021. To enhance the opportunity to find target candidates, we particularly sent the recruitment to the email list of the Chinese Studies at the University of Heidelberg. However, we merely received four applications after a week, and only one was a Sinology student. There were more Chinese natives at the Graduate School, but we preferred to employ undergraduate students for the limited budget. Therefore, we finally selected two candidates with a background in mainland

⁹ During the COVID-19 outbreak, university employees were also restricted to working from home under the lockdown policy.

China and had a recruitment interview with them separately.

Figure 1. The test sample for recruitment

To ensure the two candidates were proper to the team, we conducted an interview that included a test of typing an article from *Jing Bao*, page 2, issued on April 18, 1930, as shown in Fig. 1. They were asked to input all the Chinese characters in the article and to divide each text line correctly within 30 minutes. Their correct rates were about 91.82% and 92.61% respectively (only Chinese characters counted), which means they had some basic knowledge of the traditional form and had the promise in our task.

2.2 Training

As both editors did not have much experience in data entry and were unfamiliar with many traditional characters, we organized a weekly training course to help them quickly pick up the job. We met at the university one day per week, starting from October 16, 2021. After having four lessons, the training ended on November 6, 2021. Each class lasted for 3.5 hours, from 14:00 to 17:30. As a result, there were 14 training hours for the two new editors.

In the course, we taught them the basic concept and grammar of XML, the regulations for inputting, and the knowledge of variants (*Yitizi*). We believe learning through practice is the best way to understand the work. Therefore, they were assigned one to two pages of *Jing Bao* issued in April 1930 as a typing practice every week, and then we checked the file together in the next session. As a result, we found some problems during the training period that might inspire those interested in starting a similar project.

2.2.1 Issues of Traditional Chinese

First, both editors are native speakers of Mandarin Chinese but have no background knowledge of reading traditional Chinese texts or historical newspapers. They are only familiar with Simplified Chinese, which makes them slow in recognizing characters and results in mistakes, becoming one of the obstacles in their typing work. Since the Republican Chinese newspapers were in traditional Chinese,¹⁰ they found it difficult to identify several traditional Chinese characters and often typed the wrong ones. Particularly for the characters which are entirely different from the simplified Chinese, such as “歸/归”(gui, means “return”), “漢/汉”(han, means “Han Chinese”), “鄧/邓”(deng, a family name), “鄭/郑”(zheng, a family name), “聽/听”(ting, means “listen”), etc. This problem lasted until the last typing work of *Jing Bao* (April 1920) and was still not completely solved.

It would be better if we could employ someone from the regions such as Hong Kong and Taiwan who are familiar with traditional Chinese. However, we had few choices due to the minority of Chinese-native undergraduate students in German universities. To make up for this shortcoming, we notably spent more time explaining the differences between simplified and traditional Chinese. We pointed out some frequently appeared but easily overlooked characters. Also, we drafted a comparison table of Simplified and Traditional Chinese on our GitHub wiki page for easy checking.¹¹ Although the two editors sometimes still had problems identifying rare characters and characters with similar radicals and components, these solutions had already vastly reduced the mistakes. After training, both editors could finish typing one fold within six to seven hours.

¹⁰ The application of Simplified Chinese started after 1955. Apart from some simplified Chinese characters which had long been used, more than 80% were created and simplified after the 1950s.

¹¹ see <https://github.com/hcts-hra/ecpo-data/wiki/07-Yitizi>

2.2.2 Typing Order of the Articles

Secondly, our assistants found deciding which articles should be typed in first challenging. As the order of the pieces in the two sets of XML files should be consistent, it is necessary to set up the regulation for the typing order.

As a response, we confirmed the following regulation. First, articles on every page should be typed from top to bottom, right to left. Sometimes when the article is too long, and the rest of it goes to the next column, we should continue finishing this article in the same division and then go back to the following article. It is also the second rule that the typing order is according to the human reading habit. We try to label the GT data under the logic of a human being rather than only recording the shapes of characters. Besides articles, there are always some illustrations and photos in the middle of the texts. In this case, we should consider whether the pictures are related to the article or not. If so, the image should be incorporated into the division of the relevant article. Otherwise, the image and its caption should be grouped as another division.

2.2.3 Structure of the XML files

Figure 2. The first fold of *Jing Bao* 1930-04-27

As the image shows, each scan of *Jing Bao* is a fold, with two pages and sometimes the middle margin in between. For example, in the case of 1930 issues, page 1 is on the left and page 4 right in the first fold, while pages 2 (right) and 3 (left) are in the second fold. And we put the middle margin after the former page of the reading sequence (i.e. after page 2 and

page 4). The basic structure of this fold is like this:

```
<fold xml:id="jb_1331_1930-04-27_0001to0004">
  <div type="page" page="recto" n="1">
    .....
  </div>
  <div type="page" page="verso" n="4">
    .....
  </div>
  <div type="margin">
    .....
  </div>
</fold>12
```

As both editors did not have experience in using markup language or applying the relevant software, we spent a particular time explaining the syntax rules of extensible markup language and the meaning of the codes for our work.

¹² the complete explanation of the structure can be seen at <https://github.com/hcts-hra/ecpo-data/wiki/04-XML-Structure>

```

<div type="article" itemid="1352">
  <div>
    地中海岸Berre水上飛機場沙灘吟眺<1b/>
  </div>
  <div>
    (一枝) <1b/>
    (鷓鴣) <1b/>
    (春稿) <1b/>
  </div>
  <div>
    高天深海無窮羽。蟠闕龍<1b/>
    宮幾戰場。回首欲嗔十年<1b/>
    事。白沙州外有滄桑。<1b/>
    近數十年內、飛機潛艇、進<1b/>
    步奇速、一旦戰事勃興、高<1b/>
    天深海、無復避棄之所、猶<1b/>
    憶一九一八年之夏、開步<1b/>
    北美洲大西洋岸之梅呷、<1b/>
    <math style="transform: rotate(90deg);">Cap May</math> 其時歐戰方酣、<1b/>
    而沙頭水次、日暖風和、境<1b/>
    况之清佳、一如今日春意<1b/>
    盎然之地中海岸、而不知<1b/>
    一轉瞬間、滄<1b/>
    桑已變、世運<1b/>
    政局如是、悲歡離合之道<1b/>
    亦如是也、<1b/>
    滄海孤蹤騎鶴處。編氓犬<1b/>
    澤狎鷓身。何知人世猶波<1b/>
    惡。一葉『風擊』萬里春。<1b/>
    西文譯音『引擎』二字頗可<1b/>
    穿插入詩、飛機之發動機、<1b/>
    駕風高擊、一介編氓之水<1b/>
    手、翱翔其上、自問數十年<1b/>
    飽經世變、堪痛堪憐、反覺<1b/>
    青海白雲間、悠然憑引之<1b/>
    徒為可慶羨、十五年前老<1b/>
    友名記者某公、輕乘過此、<1b/>
    於我多所屬勉、我愧驕劣、<1b/>
    無以為報也、自巴黎寄) <1b/>
  </div>
</div>

```

Figure 3. Part of the sample XML file

As Fig. 3 shows, we describe the type, ID (in the ECPO backend), reading direction (in this case is default), content, etc., of the article in the XML file. Also, we mark line breaks and page breaks, and other information on the page and the fold. The whole structure is similar to TEI¹³ but without superfluous information, which was not needed in this task^[11]. In some special cases, such as rotated texts, we label them with specific tags with attributes. The complete XML structure can be found on the wiki page of our GitHub repository.¹⁴

It was indeed difficult for someone who did not know anything about programming to quickly understand all the codes, such as the tags `<div>` and `<p>`, etc. For this reason, the two supervisors input two issues of *Jing Bao* (April 1930) respectively, giving the editors templates to follow. Meanwhile, the meanings and functions of the editing codes were continuously explained in the weekly training courses. As we checked and compared the files together in every weekly session, it was easy to find the mistakes in the XML structures they

¹³ TEI (The Text Encoding Initiative) is a consortium which collectively develops and maintains a standard for the representation of texts in digital form, see <https://tei-c.org/>

¹⁴ <https://github.com/exc-asia-and-europe/ecpo/wiki/04-XML-Structure>

created. The usual problems in terms of structure include the misuse of the codes, wrong order of the article arrangement, and missing the end-tags such as `</div>` and `</p>`.

2.3 Data Entry

After the four-week training courses, we started to follow up on the data entry work. In order to produce duplicate files on the same issues of the tabloid for comparison, the two editors were assigned to type the same fold every week, and then we discussed their work in the following meeting. Each fold has over 20 thousand Chinese characters, in general. In the first half of our task, the editors spent 2.5 months inputting the issues of *Jing Bao* (April 1930). And then, with this experience, they became more familiar with the work when dealing with the issues of *Jing Bao* (April 1920) and spent only two months completing it. As the two editors used different input methods: one worked with Microsoft Pinyin input, and the other chose the Wubi method, it may also affect their respective input time to some extent.

During our weekly meeting, we solved the problems raised by the two editors. Nearly 90% of them were related to recognizing Chinese characters. Some were illegible because of poor printing, and most were hard to identify because they were variants or rare Chinese characters. When it came to technical issues, we recorded and discussed them with the project leader later. More details about the special issues we found and their solutions are elaborated on in Chapter 3.

2.4 Editing and Proofreading

As every fold was entered individually by the two editors simultaneously, we could quickly discover mistakes by comparing the duplicated files. We first used the comparing tools in the XML Oxygen editor to check the files, corrected the mistakes, and then merged two files into one. Then, we proofread again with the original printed pages. Generally, the editing and proofreading of each fold took six hours. This method significantly reduced errors in the final version of our GT because the two editors were supposed not to repeat the same mistakes. It also helped us discover some problems that were easily overlooked. For example, the comparison helped us discover slight differences in shapes or strokes between the characters with the same meanings but different Unicode code points, such as “尚 (U+5C1A)/尙 (U+5C19)”; “説 (U+8AAC)/說 (U+8AAA)”. Although the two editors had chosen different

variants (e.g. one chose “尙”, while another one chose “尙”) that were hard to discover with the naked eye, the comparing tools helped us find these from the duplicated files that greatly enhanced the accuracy of the input.

Moreover, we found that the two editors were likely to type the same wrong characters or make the same minor mistakes, such as skipping a whole line and forgetting to open a new paragraph. For these situations, the comparing tool was unable to discover. That’s why the proofreading process after comparing the duplicated files was always a must.

3 Special Problems During the Data Entry

We encountered various problems worth further investigating or paying attention to during the work. This section will elaborate on them for those who want to conduct a similar project as a reference.

As mentioned above, we would discuss our problems in regular meetings or post them in the issues section of our GitHub repository. Meanwhile, according to the solutions confirmed by the team members, we kept updating the Wiki pages to develop a set of work instructions with more advanced procedures and details. The challenges we faced mainly came from character encoding problems, the illegibility of the characters caused by the original poor-quality printing or the scanning of the materials with less resolution, and the uncertainties of special symbols and formats.

3.1 Encoding issues:

Our files are encoded in UTF-8 format. The Unicode standard, which defines a consistent way of encoding multilingual text^[12], is what we have been following in our work. With the complex development history, some areas in the CJK (Chinese, Japanese, Korean) language block of Unicode can be quite confusing. For example, the “CJK Compatibility Ideographs” could intensify our workload if we adopt the characters from this area. This block was initially designed to be compatible with different glyphs from multiple countries. However, its inconsistency makes some radicals irregular or have various forms. To limit the confusion, we decided not to use this particular block (U+F900...U+FAFF). Thus, we type 尙 (U+4EE4)

instead of 令 (U+F9A8), even though the latter one might visually appear more accurate than the former and has a closer look to the one printed in the newspaper.

3.1.1 Finding Characters in Unicode

We met many problems when digitizing the newspaper with Unicode, such as the codes for variants or rare characters that have not been entered into Unicode yet. It is prevalent to run into rare Chinese characters when reading old newspapers. Generally, we looked for these characters through the Unihan database, in which the characters are organized by radicals.^[13] However, Unihan-DB is not in sync with the Unicode standard stated on the website, which sometimes may slow down our editing work.¹⁵

Figure 4. The character “韉”

This character “韉”¹⁶ (韉), as the figure shows, is an extremely rare Chinese character, yet it appeared once in our data. As it was not found in Unihan-DB, the only chance for us to find the character was to manually search in the individual Unicode charts, arranged by extension number and radical stroke, respectively. After careful inquiry, we learned that this character is in fact in the area of CJK Unified Ideographs Extension F, with the code point U+2E9E8^[14]. As the characters from extension F belong to Unicode version 10, published in June 2017, they have not yet been included in Unihan-DB. That means if some rare characters cannot be found in Unihan-DB, they may be seen in the individual Unicode charts.

The above case is not common, but we did meet several times when digitizing the old newspaper, *Jing Bao*. Since *Jing Bao* was published before computers were widely used, it is understandable that the characters in the newspaper could not correspond to the codes nowadays.

Figure 5. The Character “刼”

¹⁵ “For production reasons, the version of the Unihan Database available via this lookup tool may not yet be in sync with the latest version of the Unicode Standard.” see <https://www.unicode.org/charts/unihan.html>

¹⁶ The code point is U+2E9E8. It may not correctly show in many fonts.

For example, we once found a character (Fig. 5), which should be “𠄎完 𠄎” but has not been added to the CJK blocks by today. We input “&gaiji;”, a special entity reference, to represent a character that cannot be recognized or has not been encoded. After that, we put its IDS¹⁷ description in the notes. However, it is just a compromising way. We hope the Unicode committee can increase Chinese characters to the subsequent blocks to solve the problems. The latest update was the CJK Unified Ideographs Extension H, released in September 2022.^[15]

3.1.2 Different glyphs and code points

The issue of glyphs is an essential concern in all the discussions on digital humanities in non-Latin languages. Scripts like the Chinese written language with a long development history may encounter a situation where the same character can be written in multiple ways. The vast number of Chinese characters makes it uneasy about being consistent in the encoding of Unicode. Besides, the fonts of the Chinese characters used in printing Republican newspapers differed from any standards used in today’s printing (Hong Kong, Taiwan, mainland traditional, Japan, etc.). Thus, we need to scrutinize specific radicals and components. For example, in *Jing Bao*, the character “青”, which is also a very usual component in many familiar Chinese characters such as “清”, frequently appears, rather than “青”, which is, on the contrary, more commonly used today.

The component "青" in Unicode					
青	青	清	清	晴	晴
U+9751	U+9752	U+6DF8	U+6E05	U+FA12	U+6674
靖	靖	精	精	請	請
U+FA1C	U+9756	U+FA1D	U+7CBE	U+8ACB	
情	情	蜻	蜻	靜	靜
U+60C5		U+873B		U+975C	
晴	晴	靚	澗	菁	倩
U+775B	U+5A67	U+975A	U+701E	U+83C1	U+5029

¹⁷ Ideographic Description Sequences (IDS) is used to describe CJK ideographs.

Figure 6. The Component “青” in Unicode^[16]

Let's have a further look at this character. As Fig. 6 shows, characters with the component “青” (qing, a color, means “greenish blue”) are encoded in various ways. Some with two code points are considered as different glyphs (e.g. 青/青), while some are not. In our sources, the character 青 (U+9751) is often used instead of 青 (U+9752), 清 (U+6DF8) instead of 清 (U+6E05). For the characters 晴, 靖, and 精, they have an extra code point in the CJK Compatibility Ideographs that we abandon using. However, other characters, such as 請 (U+8ACB), 情 (U+60C5), and 靜 (U+975C), are only encoded with one code point but may appear with different shapes in different fonts. In some cases, the variants were encoded with individual code points, such as 值 (U+5024), which is used in our material, while its regular font “值”, which is more commonly used nowadays, also has its code point (U+503C). However, the character “直” (U+76F4) only has one code point. As the situations were various and inconsistent, we needed to deal with the characters by case.

3.2 Printing issues:

Our materials occasionally have quality concerns because of the poor-quality printing and the scanning of the materials with too little resolution or extreme contrast. As we are creating ground truths for a machine learning task, for more accurate results, it is necessary to adhere to the principle that the data entered must be the same as what has been seen. However, it is difficult for a 21st-century reader to identify all Chinese characters in Republican newspapers, let alone that scripts can sometimes be hazy.

3.2.1 Illegible characters

Some words and symbols were too blurred to be recognized due to the poor quality of the original printing or scanning.

Figure 7. Page from ECPO

Figure 8. Page from CNBKSJ

CNBKSJ's¹⁸ version of *Jing Bao* was sometimes compared to our source. As the pictures show, CNBKSJ's scanning version has a more significant contrast with darker colours, but both versions seem to be obtained from the same original newspapers. Therefore, external references may help our editing and proofreading works but be only of limited use.

Some characters were just too infrequent or had a unique shape that our two editors were unsure whether they were included in Unicode. In such cases, we directed the editors to search on the websites such as GlyphWiki and UniHan. As supervisors, we assisted them in identifying these uncommon characters during our weekly meetings. In addition, the particular expression “&gaiji;” was used to indicate unreadable characters.

3.2.2 Rotated characters

When an individual rotated Chinese character was found in the printed newspaper, we enclosed the character with the <r> element representing rotation and used the attribute

¹⁸ CNBKSJ, 全国报刊索引(*Quan guo bao kan suo yin*), is an online database held by Shanghai Library.

style="transform: rotate(90deg);", in which the number "90" indicates the clockwise angle of rotation of the character. It is also applied to the Latin letters that are printed in a rotating direction.

Figure 9. The Rotated Character

Figure 10. The Rotated Latin Letters

In the case shown in Fig.9, the character “花” is rotated 90 degrees counterclockwise. We then encoded it as follows: `<r style="transform: rotate(-90deg);">花</r>`. The case in Fig.11 is an English phrase inside a Chinese paragraph, and the characters are rotated 90 degrees clockwise. Then we recorded the phase as: `<r style="transform: rotate(90deg);">Cap May</r>`. Another solution is to set the rotated Latin letters or scripts as default. Then, the decision can be made according to the number of Latin scripts on the pages, and, of course, the most crucial point to making the decision is to maintain consistency.

3.3 Variants issues:

As mentioned before, the font used in the Republican publications was not the same as any fonts used in the present-day Chinese language printing industry. Therefore, it was necessary to summarize a complete table of Republican newspaper variants corresponding to the current commonly used characters. The table can be found on the Wiki page. We constantly updated the table with the variants we discovered during the editing and proofreading works.

The characters in the Republican newspapers may have different shapes or positions of their radicals or components from today. For example, the component “丿” is usually written as “八” in Republican newspapers. Therefore, we input “尙”(U+5C19) rather than “尚”(U+5C1A). Sometimes, a variant that is classified as Simplified Chinese after 1949 was

frequently printed in *Jing Bao*, such as the use of “幫” (U+5E2E) instead of “幫”(U+5E6B), which is now regarded as Traditional Chinese.

There was also a special case where it was obvious that a typo was used in the newspaper, some of which may be due to the misuse of characters with similar shapes or the publisher’s operational errors. In this case, we did not correct these mistakes because we aimed to provide the machine with accurate data to perform optical character recognition rather than editing the digitized newspapers.

4 Evaluation of blind double-keying mode

Developing a proper working model was also vital for the purpose of this task. Thus, we evaluated our blind double-keying mode, reflecting on its strengths and weaknesses.

The two editors, labeled as A and B, should theoretically refrain from exchanging input data and technical details with each other to avoid affecting the following comparisons. In order to achieve the goal, they were asked to create two separate branches with their names on GitHub. All their work has been done within their branch to avoid file conflicts. When each section of work was complete, they could submit them by pressing “pull requests”.

Sometimes one of the editors may carelessly miss several characters or even an entire paragraph line. When comparing both files, we could quickly find these omissions due to inadvertence. Since the two editors used different input methods, one was Microsoft Pinyin, and the other was Wubi, comparing the output could also effectively avoid possible bias caused by the single input method. For instance, when the Pinyin of the character “說” is entered by using the Microsoft Pinyin Input Method (Traditional Chinese), the first option is “說” (U+8AAA). But when the Pinyin of the term “說話” (shuohua, speak) is entered, the character “說” in the first option becomes the variant “說” (U+8AAC). Our blind double-keying working pattern allowed us to be more sensitive to cases with such subtle differences.

However, a few things should be kept in mind when using this working method. One possible situation was that the two editors coincidentally made the same mistakes. It would not be

shown up when comparing documents and could be easily overlooked. For this reason, we still cross-referenced the merged documents with the original materials after the comparison procedure in order to ensure that no mistakes were made in the digitized files. Here, we would like to list some cases found during the process.

The unfamiliarity with traditional Chinese characters caused them to misrecognize some characters simultaneously. For example, they both mistook the “晝” (zhou, daytime, U+665D) for “畫” (hua, painting, U+756B), as whose simplified form “画” has an entirely different shape. Therefore, professional guidance and timely feedback on the work is vital for improving the quality of the follow-up typing. But, of course, it also means more time and effort are needed.

Nevertheless, things are not perfect. For example, when we processed images for OCR, we could still find a few errors, such as missing characters, which might have been accidentally deleted by mistake.

5 Conclusion

With proper planning and scheduling, our project ran successfully. In the end, we achieved the following data results (April 1939 data from previous project).

<i>Jing bao</i> April 1939	10 issues, 40 folds
<i>Jing bao</i> April 1930	10 issues, 20 folds
<i>Jing bao</i> April 1920	10 issues, 20 folds

Table 2. Numbers of GT productions

As for the text Ground Truth, the outcome contains approximately 1.324 million characters in local XML format. The average character content is 16.554 chars/fold. The typing speed of the two editors reduced from 10h/fold at the beginning to 6h/fold. Aside from the text, there is also the geometry Groundtruth which holds 116 folds, 10714 shapes, an average of 92.36

shapes/fold.

Our project has already tested the effect of the ground truth of 1939 issues. As Konstantin Henke indicates in his thesis, the final accuracy of the OCR combining the pre-training and fine-tuning reaches 97%. That shows our project achieved significant results.^[17] We hope the 1930 and 1920 materials can get an even better result. Then, the methods and tools mentioned above are expected to be applied to similar tabloids issued in the Republican period and then to a broader range of other materials.

From the perspective of non-Latin material, our project makes some contributions regarding the operations of the task and the solutions to the problems. On the one hand, the paper, as a working report, shows how the training of editors, the data entry of the newspapers to an XML file and the editing and proofreading procedure were developed. On the other hand, it indicates the reasons for setting up the project, the problems and difficulties that the teams encountered and the solutions for those issues, sharing the experiences of building up the ground truth for an OCR system for non-Latin languages.

References:

[1] ARNOLD M, 2022. “Multilingual Research Projects: Non-Latin Script Challenges for Making Use of Standards, Authority Files, and Character Recognition.” [J/OL]. Digital Studies/Le champ numérique 12(1): 1–36. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.16995/dscn.8110>.

[2] MAGNER T F, 1974. “The Latin Alphabet and the Languages of China.”[J]. The Journal of General Education 26(3): 205–18. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/27796437>.

[3] MAHONY S, 2018. “Cultural Diversity and the Digital Humanities.”[J]. Fudan Journal of the Humanities and Social Sciences 11(3): 371–88. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s40647-018-0216-0>.

[4] SPENCE P J, BRANDAO R, 2021. “Towards Language Sensitivity and Diversity in the Digital Humanities”[J/OL]. Digital Studies / Le champ numérique 11(1). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.16995/dscn.8098>

- [5] ARNOLD M, (2021, March 23). *Ground Truth, Neural Networks, OCR: Towards Full Text of Republican China Newspapers* [Video]. Association for Asian Studies 2021 Virtual Annual Conference, AAS2021, virtual. <https://tinyurl.com/ecpo-intro>.
- [6] ARNOLD M, HESSEL L. (2019). *Transforming data silos into knowledge: Early Chinese Periodicals Online (ECPO)*. [P] E-Science-Tage 2019: Data to Knowledge, Heidelberg. <https://doi.org/DOI:10.11588/heidok.00027325>
- [7] 张玮. 民国报纸数字化验收常见问题研究——以国家图书馆为例[J]. 图书情报研究, 2019, 12 (03) : 72-79.
- [8] 曹鑫新. 浅谈民国报纸数字资源建设质效提升——以国家图书馆为例[J]. 数字与缩微影像, 2023 (3) : 11-14.
- [9] 肖红, 槐燕. 民国报纸数字化实践中的质检问题探析[J]. 图书馆学研究, 2017 (07) : 61-78+87
- [10] 祝均宙. 晚清民國年間小報源流特點探究[M]. 圖鑑百年文獻. 新北市: 華藝學術出版社, 2013.
- [11] *The TEI Infrastructure—The TEI Guidelines* [EB/OL]. Accessed on November 29, 2022, from <https://tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/en/html/ST.html>
- [12] The Unicode Consortium (Ed.). (2020). *The Unicode Standard, Version 13.0 – Core Specification* [EB/OL]. Unicode, Inc. <https://www.unicode.org/versions/Unicode13.0.0/UnicodeStandard-13.0.pdf>
- [13] JENKINS J H, COOK R, LUNDE K, 2021. “UAX #38: Unicode Han Database (Unihan).”[EB/OL]//Unicode Technical Reports. <https://www.unicode.org/reports/tr38/>.
- [14] CJK Unified Ideographs Extension F [EB/OL]//The Unicode Standard, Version 15.0, accessed on November 29, 2022. <https://unicode.org/charts/PDF/U2CEB0.pdf>
- [15] Unicode, I. (n.d.). Announcing The Unicode® Standard, Version 15.0 [EB/OL].

Accessed December 7, 2022, from <http://blog.unicode.org/2022/09/announcing-unicode-standard-version-150.html>

[16] 說文:unicode 摧殘正體字, 刻石錄 [EB/OL]. Accessed on December 7, 2022, from <https://founder.acgvlyric.org/iu/doku.php/%e8%aa%aa%e6%96%87:unicode%e6%91%a7%e6%ae%98%e6%ad%a3%e9%ab%94%e5%ad%97>

[17] HENKE K, 2021. “Building and Improving an OCR Classifier for Republican Chinese Newspaper Text.”[D]. B.A. thesis. Department of Computational Linguistics, Heidelberg University. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.11588/heidok.00030845>.